

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

**Deliverable D10.4
Second Mid-term Dissemination
Report**

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
ASNT	American Society For Nondestructive Testing
ATCA	Air Traffic Control Association
ATM	Air Traffic Management
BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line of Sight
CANSO	Civil Air Navigation Services Organisation
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CTO	Chief Technology Officer
DARPA	Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency
DIH	Digital Innovation Hubs
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
ERF	European Robotics Forum
EU	European Union
EUROCAE	European Organisation for Civil Aviation Equipment
GA	Grant Agreement
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSA	General Services Administration
IDEM	Innovation, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IRF	International Road Federation
ISUDEF	International Symposium on Unmanned Systems and the Defence Industry
KPI	Key Performance Index
NDT	Nondestructive Testing
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
ROS	Robot Operating System
SMEs	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises
UAE	United Arab Emirates
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
URS	Unmanned Robotic System

Table 1. List of acronyms

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The current document contains the second communication and dissemination report summarizing the activities carried out during the second period of PILOTING Project (M19-M36). The aim of this deliverable is to collect all the actions focused on promoting and disseminating the project and analyze their results and impact, as it is defined in the previous deliverable D10.2 “Exploitation and Dissemination Plan” where the dissemination KPIs were defined.

1.2 Scope of the document

This deliverable covers the activities carried out within task T10.3 “Dissemination, communication, and engaging the I&M community” in the second reporting period of the project. Then, this document complements the deliverable D10.3 “Frist Mid-term Dissemination report” and it explains in detail the different communication and dissemination actions executed during this second period. Also, and as part of the managing activity of the project, it updates the dissemination related KPIs of the project.

1.3 Structure of the document

This report has been structured according to the dissemination/communication tools defined in the deliverable D10.2 to each target audience group:

- Section 1 defines the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable.
- Section 2 presents the main communication actions carried out in this 2nd period of the PILOTING project.
- Section 3 presents the main dissemination actions that took place in the M19-M36 period.
- Section 4 presents the monitoring actions of the KPIs defined in the D10.2.
- Section 5 explains the main conclusions extracted from the analysis of this Second Mid-term Dissemination Report.

2. Communication tools

2.1 Visual Identity

The project's visual identity was developed at the beginning of the project and has been maintained in all publications and presentations related to the project. The visual identity includes the project logo (see Figure 1), flyer, roll-up, poster, templates (to documents and presentations) and public presentations templates that can be used when the partners have presented their work.

Figure 1. PILOTING logo.

During this period, a new version of the PILOTING project public presentation, more focused on the presentation of the project outcomes, has been developed (see Annex I: PILOTING Public Presentation. New version.).

2.2 Project Website

The PILOTING project website (<https://piloting-project.eu/>) has been updated to include more detailed information and be more attractive, especially, since the project dissemination related to the pilot outcomes has been reinforced. Also, the reviewers' comments from the 1st review report have been considered in the update and upgrades of the PILOTING web site.

The main updates have been focused to make the website more attractive and easier to navigate, facilitating the way general public is able to find specific information. The objective is to attract the public, especially large companies and SMEs of the PILOTING sectors.

Below, the main changes introduced in the PILOTING website during this period have been summarized.

➤ **GENERAL UPDATES:**

- Modification of the PILOTING website menu, removing the H2020 logo and adding the European Union flag, following the recommendations from the [European Commission](#).

Figure 2. Menu of the PILOTING project website: Former (left); Current (right).

- Following the EU guides, the message required, mentioning that the project has been co-funded by the European Union within the H2020 programme, has been added.

Figure 3. PILOTING project website: "Home" footer.

- A description of each section has been added at the header (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. PILOTING "News" tab. Short description added at the header: Former (left); Current (right).

➤ PROJECT OVERVIEW

The Project Overview section is the section that most changes has suffered. Firstly, the "PILOTING Uses Cases" and the "Cooperation" sections were added to the menu and their format has been improved constantly. The main aims of these sections are explained below:

1. PILOTING Uses Cases: This section presents the inspection uses cases that will be the subject of PILOTING Project: Refineries, Viaducts/Bridges and Tunnels.

2. **Cooperation:** In Cooperation section, a list of relevant projects with whom PILOTING is collaborating is presented.

With regards to the existing sections within “Project Overview”, the most important upgrades that have taken place are the new format of “Objectives” and a restructuring to improve the aesthetics of the information explained.

Figure 5. PILOTING “Project Overview-> Objectives” tab: Former (left); Current (right).

➤ CONSORTIUM

Restructuration of the information from each member of the association, standing out the experience that each member can contribute to the consortium and the addition of a new header on the main page.

➤ NEWS

The news on the web page have been classified by the publication year and in groups of three pieces by line. Also, the format has been changed (see Figure 6). The news section has been restructured with the addition of a short description on the cover page and even, the rewrite of some of them to make each piece of news more attractive to the public of the PILOTING Project.

Figure 6. PILOTING project website: "News" tab: Former (above); Current (below).

➤ **PUBLIC MATERIAL:**

This section has also changed with important updates. To explain this, both sections will be shown separately.

1. Publications and data sets: The ZENODO logo and a brief description have been added to the headboard.

Figure 7. PILOTING project website “Publications and data sets” tab: Former (above); Current (below).

2. **Multimedia:** The information in the Multimedia section has been restructured to better differentiate the contents published. First, it has been divided into three main topics: Videos, Podcasts and Newsletters (the projects Newsletters have been added to the multimedia tab).
 - **Videos:** The videos developed related to the PILOTING Project have been divided in the following sections: PILOTING I&M Platform, PILOTING Demonstrations & Experiments, PILOTING Youtube Series: Meet our inspection robots, PILOTING Workshops, PILOTING Project presentation, and Previous projects videos. A description of the content of each section and each video has been included. The evolution of this tab is showed in the Figure 8.

Figure 8. PILOTING project website “Public Material -> Multimedia” tab: new sections.

- Podcasts: The PILOTING podcast series “PILOTING: Inspection Gadget” published until now are contained in this section.
- Newsletters: In this part, it is possible to find each one of the Newsletters that the PILOTING consortium has published.

In the next three figures, it can be observed the evolution of the Multimedia Section of the project website during these first three years of the project.

Figure 9. PILOTING project website “Public Material -> Multimedia” tab: Original Version.

PROJECT VIDEOS

Meet our inspection robots: RISING (episode 5)

5th episode of the PILOTING YouTube serie...

Meet our inspection robots: AEROCAM (episode 4)

4th episode of the PILOTING YouTube serie...

European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance

PODCAST

Episode 10

Escuchar en App

Reproducir en navegador

Episode 9

Escuchar en App

Reproducir en navegador

Episode 8

Escuchar en App

Reproducir en navegador

Figure 10. PILOTING project website “Public Material -> Multimedia” tab: Second Version.

VIDEOS

PILOTING I&M PLATFORM

The PILOTING I&M Platform is a key tool to manage the mission of the robotic vehicles and control the operation. Here you will find the latest multimedia content about this brand new development.

PILOTING I&M Platform – Workflow

The PILOTING I&M Platform is part of the PILOTING ecosystem. This is an integrated and unified system of hardware and software components to increase the efficiency and quality of inspection and maintenance activities.

PILOTING DEMONSTRATIONS & EXPERIMENTS

Inside the PILOTING project framework several technical demonstrations will be held in the scenarios of the experiments and robots.

AEROX Experiment – Inspection of Large Structures

PILOTING Project presents new updates on the development and experiments of its robotic platforms. The last episode of the series of experiments of PILOTING's robotic solutions presents the AEROX experiment, an aerial platform developed by CATEC for its operation in the inspection of large structures.

BIKE Experiment – Internal Inspection of Pressure Vessels

PILOTING Project presents new updates on the development and experiments of its robotic platforms. The fifth episode of the series of experiments about PILOTING's robotic solutions brings you BIKE, the crawler solution developed by WTR designed for internal inspection of pressure vessels.

PILOTING YOUTUBE SERIES: MEET OUR INSPECTION ROBOTS

Meet Our Inspection Robots. Youtubes series elaborated by PILOTING consortium and focused on introducing each robot developed within the project to bring them closer to the I&M community.

Meet our inspection robots: RISING (episode 5)

In this 5th episode of the Youtube series "Meet our inspection robots" H2020 PILOTING Project presents the RISING robot, Robotnik's mobile manipulator specially designed for intervention, reconnaissance and EOD missions.

Meet our inspection robots: AEROCAM (episode 4)

"Meet our Inspection Robots" PILOTING youtube series episode 4. In this episode, Rafael Caballero, research expert from CATEC shows the AEROCAM, a novel visual inspection drone.

PODCAST

PILOTING consortium has a podcast series, "PILOTING Inspection Gadget", with interviews with key people in the I&M sector, aims to obtain feedback from the I&M community and positioning the PILOTING consortium as a reference in the development of robotic solutions for I&M applications.

Episode 11

In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 11, Andrea Berra (<https://www.aerotrains-etn.eu/esr-14>), PhD student from the University of Seville and Early Stage Research in the CATEC Technological Centre, presents the AERO-TRAIN Project.

Escuchar en App
Reproducir en navegador

Episode 10

Prof. Cédric Pradalier, from the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique – Dream Lab, Project Coordinator of the H2020 project Bugwright2 (<https://www.bugwright2.eu/>) presents the project.

Escuchar en App
Reproducir en navegador

Figure 11. PILOTING project website “Public Material -> Multimedia” tab: Third Version.

In addition, the website provides a contact point for the different target groups of the PILOTING project, the email address: piloting-project@catec.aero.

On the other hand, Figure 12 shows how the average PILOTING website audience has evolved from M19 to M36 (up to December 15th). It is important to point out that the peak of impressions has been close to 1200 impressions (around the viaduct experiments) while there has been stability in the range of 400 to 800 impressions during this period, while in the M1-M18 period the average impressions could not reach the peak of 600 impressions.

Figure 12: PILOTING website statistics.

As Table 2 shows, most of the visits are from consortium countries, demonstrating the PILOTING partners’ efforts to disseminate the project. As it can be seen, the number of the first 10 countries

ordered by clicks in the PILOTING website adds 712 clicks with respect to the 656 from the previous period. It is also noticed an increase in the number of impressions that grew from 32.221 in the last period up to 39.783, which makes a difference of more than 7.000 new impressions that represents an increase of a 23,5%.

Country	Clicks	Impressions
Spain	346	4.834
Greece	114	5.624
Switzerland	54	2.940
United Kingdom	53	5.552
France	35	2.709
Germany	27	3.773
Norway	25	739
Netherlands	24	1.751
Italy	23	2.622
United States	11	9.239

Table 2. PILOTING website: Origin of visits

2.3 Social media

Social media has played a key role in the PILOTING Project dissemination activities since the beginning of the initiative. It has allowed the consortium to maximise the impact and visibility to project events and news to the general public. These dissemination tasks have relapsed on two social media accounts:

- **PILOTING LinkedIn profile**

The social network LinkedIn has contributed to the development of the PILOTING project by increasing communication between the project and its target group. This has been important due to the rapprochement between the two, facilitated by the dissemination processes that have been carried out on this platform.

The PILOTING LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/h2020-piloting-project/>) (see Figure 13) was launched at the end of 2019 and, since then, it has been in a constant increase both in posts and followers.

Figure 13. PILOTING LinkedIn Profile.

At this point in the project (M36), PILOTING Project LinkedIn account has 440 followers.

The following figure illustrates the evolution of the profiles during the second period from M19 up to M36. In Figure 14, it can be seen the relation between the increase of visits to the profile and the publications of the profile due to the publication of episodes from YouTube Series or PILOTING Podcast Series.

At the moment this deliverable has been written, PILOTING LinkedIn profile has 440 followers while at the end of the M1-M18 period they were 339 followers. This means an increase of 30% for 101 new followers.

Figure 14. New followers of the PILOTING LinkedIn profile in the last 12 months of the project.

- **PILOTING Twitter profile**

Twitter PILOTING account (https://twitter.com/PILOTING_EU) (see Figure 15) was also launched at the end of 2019 and it has mainly used to disseminate results and other news related to the project.

Twitter is considered a more informal platform, but this presents several benefits. First, this is a bigger social media than LinkedIn where all types of individuals can be found. It forces the users to type the publications within maximum 280 characters, what makes it very easy to read them. In addition, it allows the users to share content and multimedia in real time which can be very productive in the framework of dissemination activities.

From the first steps, CATEC has continued to manage both profiles in social networks as project coordinator.

During the M19-M36 period, the PILOTING Twitter profile has published 1,7 tweets per week on average.

Figure 15 shows the current state of the Twitter account of the PILOTING Project. Right now, the account has 352 followers, while at the end of the first period, we had only 255 followers. Then, in this second period, we have increased the number of followers by 72%.

Figure 15. PILOTING Twitter Profile.

- **PILOTING iVoox profile**

For the publications of the Podcast Series: PILOTING Inspection Gadget, it was decided to create a profile in iVoox. iVoox is a platform that enables users to listen to, download, and share audio content in diverse categories, including technology, with open access.

The iVoox new channel, named “PILOTING: Inspection gadget” was launched in February 2021. Nowadays the channel has 339 reproductions, and it contains a total of 15 episodes with interviews with personalities related to the I&M sector.

Figure 16. PILOTING iVoox profile

2.4 Periodic press-releases

PILOTING Consortium has published periodic press releases about specific PILOTING's achievements that can be interesting to the industrial companies, SEMs and the general public. This press releases help us to attract the attention of general and specialized media that then decides to create a specific report of the PILOTING project.

Table 3 shows the news/articles disseminated through the PILOTING consortium countries in M19-M36 period.

Date	Topic	Venue	Evidence
02/11/2021	The PILOTING partners, Sigurd Mørkved, gives an interview presenting PILOTING project.	Norwegian industrial magazine	https://www.samferdselinfra.no/bladarkiv/samferdsel-infrastruktur-03-utgave-2021/ p37-39
25/04/2022 26/0/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Electronic Media Local Media	https://www.tribunadeandalucia.es/la-tecnologia-robotica-del-catec-parte-del-proyecto-europeo-mas-ambicioso-sobre-movilidad-aerea-urbana/
25/04/2022 28/0/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Electronic Media Local Media	https://actualidad aeroespacial.com/malaga-acogel-primeras-pruebas-de-validacion-de-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-para-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras/ https://www.lavanguardia.com/local/sevilla/20220425/8220089/malaga-acoge-primeras-pruebas-validacion-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-inspeccion-infraestructuras.html

			<p>https://www.laopiniondemalaga.es/malaga/2022/04/25/malaga-acoge-primeras-pruebas-validacion-65359324.html</p> <p>https://www.malagahoy.es/malaga/Malaga-inspeccion-infraestructuras-envejecidas-robots_0_1677732584.html</p> <p>https://www.europapress.es/andalucia/malaga-00356/noticia-alora-malaga-acoge-primeras-pruebas-validacion-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-inspeccionar-infraestructuras-20220425110833.html</p> <p>https://www.msn.com/es-es/noticias/tecnologia/m%3%A1laga-acoge-las-primeras-pruebas-de-validaci%C3%B3n-de-tecnolog%C3%ADa-rob%C3%B3tica-a%C3%A9rea-para-inspecci%C3%B3n-de-infraestructuras/ar-AAWyVr5</p> <p>https://www.noticiasde.es/nd/andalucia/malaga/malaga-acoge-las-primeras-pruebas-de-validacion-de-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-para-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras/</p> <p>https://www.aeropolis.es/boletin/catec-aplica-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-para-la-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras/</p> <p>http://www.gentedigital.es/malaga/noticia/3370385/malaga-acoge-las-primeras-pruebas-de-validacion-de-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-para-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras/</p> <p>https://www.teleprensa.com/articulo/malaga/malaga-acoge-primeras-pruebas-validacion-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-inspeccion-infraestructuras/202204251112381192049.html</p> <p>https://tedae.org/es/noticias/malaga-acoge-las-primeras-pruebas-de-validacion-de-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-para-la-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras</p> <p>https://soldigital.es/2022/04/25/malaga-acoge-las-primeras-pruebas-de-validacion-de-tecnologia-robotica-aerea-para-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras/</p> <p>https://www.infodron.es/texto-diario/mostrar/3581041/aerocam-supera-pruebas-inspeccion-infraestructuras-drones-proyecto-europeo-piloting</p> <p>https://www.diariodesevilla.es/empresas-al-dia/FAD-Catec-convierte-robots-vigilantes-infraestructuras_0_1678032774.html</p>
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26/04/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Printed Media Local Media	Málaga Hoy. Pág 14.
17/05/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Electronic Media Local Media	https://www.rpas-drones.com/primeras-pruebas-de-validacion-de-aerocam-para-la-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras/
27/07/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Printed Media Local Media	Málaga Hoy. Pág 14.
27/07/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Printed Media Local Media	Málaga Hoy. Pág 18.
26/07/2022 27/07/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Electronic Media Local Media	https://www.diariosigloxxi.com/texto-ep/mostrar/20220726152851/robots-aereos-andaluces-mejoran-inspeccion-evaluacion-infraestructuras-civiles-envejecidas https://www.europapress.es/andalucia/malaga-00356/noticia-robots-aereos-andaluces-mejoran-inspeccion-evaluacion-infraestructuras-civiles-envejecidas-20220726131828.html https://www.diariosur.es/interior/piloting-proyecto-europeo-robotica-20220726154719-nt.html https://www.lavanguardia.com/local/sevilla/20220726/8432571/robots-aereos-andaluces-mejoran-inspeccion-evaluacion-infraestructuras-civiles-envejecidas.html https://www.ceacop.com/malaga-piloting-robotica-e-inteligencia-artificial-con-sello-europeo-para-optimizar-el-mantenimiento-de-infraestructuras/ https://www.defensa.com/aeronautica-y-espacio/robots-aereos-andaluces-inspeccion-infraestructuras-envejecidas https://www.tribunadeandalucia.es/robots-aereos-andaluces-mejoran-la-inspeccion-y-evaluacion-de-infraestructuras-civiles-envejecidas/ https://sevilla.abc.es/economia/robots-aereos-andaluces-inspeccionan-puentes-viaductos-viejos-20220726103734-nts.html
28/07/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álora.	Electronic Media Local Media	https://www.airline92.com/drones/robots-aereos-andaluces-inspeccion-infraestructuras-envejecidas
01/08/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about	Electronic Media	https://i-sense.iccs.gr/news/validation-tests-of-aerial-robotics-technology-for-infrastructure-inspection-in-piloting-project/

	inspection in a viaduct in Álorá.		
10/08/2022	The PILOTING partners give an interview about inspection in a viaduct in Álorá.	Electronic Media Local Media	https://www.rpas-drones.com/piloting-robots-aereos-para-inspeccion-de-infraestructuras/
18/09/2022	The PILOTING partner, Antidio Viguria, gives an interview presenting PILOTING project.	Printed Media Local Media	ABC Empresa. Pág 7.
05/11/2022	The PILOTING partner, Antidio Viguria, gives an interview explaining his point of view of the market situation and prospects	Electronic media	https://industrytalks.es/drones-un-mercado-en-plena-expansion-pero-aun-por-madurar-a-escala-industrial/
16/11/2022	The PILOTING partner, Henrik Lundkvist, gives an interview presenting PILOTING project.	Electronic Media Local Media	https://www.at.no/anlegg/raskere-og-billigere-tunnel-arbeid-med-roboter/714210 https://nyheter.byggfakta.no/roboter-i-fremtidens-tunnelarbeid-311145/nyhet.html https://www.bygg.no/jobber-for-raskere-og-billigere-tunnelarbeid-med-roboter-vil-ha-med-seg-norske-selskaper/1512052!/ https://www.veier24.no/artikler/ny-robotteknologi-klar-for-test-ved-inspeksjon-av-norske-tunneler/523727 https://www.samferdselinfra.no/raskere-og-billigere-tunnelarbeid-med-roboter/ https://www.radionordkapp.no/pressemelding/raske-re-og-billigere-tunnelarbeid-med-roboter/ https://gemini.no/2022/11/robotinspektorene-kommer/

Table 3. Local media presence.

2.5 Electronic newsletters

PILOTING electronic newsletters have been periodically launched around every six months, providing updates and relevant information about the project. As shown in Table 4, three PILOTING newsletter issues have been published during this period.

In the current period, three newsletters have been published and one more is expected to be launched in January 2023, this makes a total increase of a 100% with respect to the previous period.

Issue	Topics	Publication date	Partners responsible
3rd newsletter	Activities carried out by the PILOTING consortium during the 1st half of 2021 and presentation of the PILOTING	July 2021	CATEC-Overall Coordination All partners-Contribution

	vehicles and main advances in the PILOTING I&M platform		
4th newsletter	This newsletter covers the activities carried out in the first months of the 2 nd project period (M18-M24), focusing on the presentation of PILOTING Uses Cases.	February 2022	CATEC-Overall Coordination All partners- Contribution
5th newsletter	This newsletter covers the presentation of the main development within the project: the PILOTING I&M platform, and its work alongside the other parts of the PILOTING system.	August 2022	CATEC-Overall Coordination All partners- Contribution
6 th newsletter	A sixth newsletter will be delivered by the beginning of 2023 collecting the results from the last large-scale demonstrations within the PILOTING Project.	January 2023	CATEC-Overall Coordination All partners- Contribution

Table 4. Overview of newsletters.

The newsletters have been disseminated through the PILOTING website ('Public Material Tab'), PILOTING social networks and the PILOTING User Group that currently has 215 members (see Section 3.1).

2.6 New Communication Channels

New communication channels were developed in the framework of the PILOTING Project due to the lack of physical events and the temporary impossibility of attending presential events since the appearance of the COVID-19 pandemic. This new communication format has been very successful, which is why the PILOTING consortium decided to continue publishing its content even though the physical events have returned since March 2022.

The creation of content has followed the working line established in the previous period within two main platforms:

- "Meet Our Inspection Robots" YouTube Series Videos.
- "PILOTING Inspection Gadget" PILOTING Podcasts Series.

Moreover, a third multimedia channel has been created to disseminate the main results of the project demonstrations.

- "PILOTING Demonstrations & Experiments" YouTube Series Videos.

In the following sections, it will be described the specific dissemination material that was generated and disseminated during the M19-M36 period.

2.6.1 YouTube Series Video: “Meet Our Inspection Robots”

Following the success of the AeroX, CART and BIKE robotic platforms videos, the members of the PILOTING Project have continued to focus on dissemination through audio-visual platforms. In this period, three new autonomous platforms have been presented.

This Youtube Series is available through the [PILOTING website multimedia section](#) and the PILOTING social networks ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)). Table 5 summarises the “Meet Our Inspection Robots” episodes published in the M19-M36 period. As it can be seen, the number of publications equals the same publications in the First Dissemination Report with 3 new videos uploaded.

Episode	Publication date	Vehicle	Partners responsible
Episode 4	27/08/2021	AEROCAM robot	CATEC
Episode 5	19/01/2022	RISING ground robot	ROBOTNIK
Episode 6	30/11/2022	HYBRID robot	CATEC

Table 5. Public episodes of the PILOTING YouTube Series:” Meet our inspections robots”

2.6.2 Podcast Series: “PILOTING Inspection gadget”

New episodes of the PILOTING Podcasts Series have been released during the second period, with the participation of leading personalities in the I&M Industry. Feedback from previous interviews has helped to improve the quality and quantity of the episodes and to position the PILOTING consortium as a reference in the development of robotic solutions for I&M applications.

This Podcast Series “PILOTING Inspection Gadget” is available through the [PILOTING iVoox profile](#), the [PILOTING website multimedia section](#) and the PILOTING social networks ([LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#)). Table 6 summarises which “PILOTING Inspection gadget” episodes have been published in the M19-M36 period.

The PILOTING Podcast has published 10 new videos in this period, this represents an increase of a 100% in the audio-visual content positioning itself as one of the most remarkable indicators.

Episode	Publication date	Topic
Episode 6	27/07/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 6 , Marvin Dechene, head of technology and responsible for drone inspections at APPLUS RVIS (https://www.applus.com/global/en/), talks about the benefits of using drones for inspection duties in the industry and the feedback from actual inspectors using robotic systems. He also gives his opinion on the barriers to using the technology and the acceptance of technological advances.
Episode 7	26/10/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 7 , Prof. Anibal Ollero, full professor at University of Seville and Scientific Advisor at FADA-CATEC, presents AERIAL-CORE H2020 project (https://aerial-core.eu/), which aims at developing novel aerial manipulating robotics technologies for the inspection and

		maintenance of infrastructures in strict collaboration with human workers.
Episode 8	18/11/2021	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 8 , Belen Riveiro, associate professor at the University of Vigo and Project Coordinator of SAFEWAY H2020 (https://www.safeway-project.eu/en), presents a general overview of the project, which leads to significantly improved resilience of transport infrastructures, developing a holistic toolset with transversal application to anticipate and mitigate the effects extreme events at all modes of disaster cycle.
Episode 9	12/01/2022	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 9 , Kostas Alexis, full profesor in NTNU (https://www.ntnu.edu/employees/konstantinos.alexis), talks about his experience en robotic competition “DARPA Subterranean Challenge”, of which his team was the winner.
Episode 10	03/03/2022	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 10 , Prof. Cédric Pradalier, from the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique – Dream Lab (https://dream.georgiatech-metz.fr/), Project Coordinator of the H2020 project Bugwright2 (https://www.bugwright2.eu/) presents the project.
Episode 11	25/04/2022	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 11 , Andrea Berra (https://www.aerotrains-etn.eu/esr-14), PhD student from the University of Seville and Early Stage Research in the CATEC Technological Centre, presents the AERO-TRAIN Project. AERO-TRAIN Project is a Marie Curie Research Project and the first research base train initiative in aerial robotics for inspection and maintenance. His research focuses on developing guidance and control algorithms for aerial robotics for contact-based inspection.
Episode 12	26/05/2022	In this episode , Juan Román, General Director of Andalucía Aerospace (https://andaluciaaerospace.com/en/), explains how the cluster adds value to aeronautical companies, highlights the relevance of the Andalusian region in the drone sector and takes an overall view of the future of the industry in our country and the rest of the world.
Episode 13	13/06/2022	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget-episode 13 , Alexandra Florin, Co-chair at Working Group 105 at EUROCAE (https://www.eurocae.net/) and Aviation Technical Standards Manager at Wing (https://wing.com/) presents EUROCAE (European Organization for Civil Aviation Equipment) and its main activity.
Episode 14	27/10/2022	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget: episode 14 , Luis Moratinos, Geomatics Manager at Ferroviario Construction (https://www.ferrovial.com/), remarks the main benefits of PILOTING solutions for I&M activities, the future of these novel technologies and the difficulties they have to overcome from the point of view of a large infrastructure company.
Episode 15	January 2023	In PILOTING Inspection Gadget episode 15, José Solis, project coordinator of OMICRON project presents OMICRON H2020 project, and their activities related with the use of robotics in inspection of roadways and highways.

Table 6. Public episodes of the PILOTING Podcast Series:” Inspection Gadget”

This Podcast series will continue during the third period due to the success among the different stakeholders of the I&M community and even to increase the coordination with other H2020 projects related to I&M.

2.6.3 YouTube Series Video: “PILOTING Demonstrations & Experiments”

Due to the latest tests and demonstrations carried out in the project the website has included a new subsection (under the Multimedia section) named “PILOTING Demonstrations & Experiments” where all the content related to the Demonstrations and Experiments of the robotic platforms can be found.

This section aims to share the results from the tests completed in the last period to make the PILOTING robotic platforms and their skills known to society. Here, a total amount of 8 videos can be found: 2 videos are related to the large-scale demonstration in the viaduct scenarios whereas the remaining 6 short videos will deal with the experiments of the robotic solutions at the refinery. The videos of the tunnel scenarios are still in progress, and once they are ready (expected January 2023), they will also be uploaded into the webpage.

Title	Publication date	Vehicle	Description
1st large scale demonstration in the viaduct scenario Agenda	07/09/2022	AEROCAM & VIADDRONE	This video shows the flight demo of AEROCAM and VIADDRONE, which were designed and developed by FADA-CATEC and USE and also here we explain which are the benefits and results of the application of robotics technologies researched inside the project framework for the inspection and maintenance industry and tasks.
1st large scale demonstration in the viaduct scenario	09/09/2022	AEROCAM & VIADDRONE	This video shows the flight demonstration of the two robotic platforms which were tested and demonstrated in the following PILOTING Uses Cases: AEROCAM (robot designed for visual inspection) and VIADDRONE (robot designed for contact inspection on viaducts).
Aerial reconnaissance for AI detection of corrosion and defects	5/12/2022	AEROCAM	In this first episode of the series about demonstrations, AEROCAM will perform its operation in aerial reconnaissance operation for AI detection of corrosion and defects in a real environment.
Navigation and manipulation of equipment	7/12/2022	UGV	Continuing with the series of demonstrations, this time it is the turn of the UGV to show us its operation in navigation and equipment handling.
Navigation and image capture of equipment	12/12/2022	RISING	On this occasion, the RISING vehicle, developed by ROBOTNIK, will showcase its navigation and image capture capabilities of the equipment in a real test environment.
Mobile crawler for inspection	14/12/2022	HYBRID	In the fourth episode of the series of demonstrations, HYBRID, the crawler robotic

of pipes at height			platform developed by CATEC, will show its skills for pipes inspection at height.
Internal Inspection of Pressure Vessels	19/12/2022	BIKE	The fifth episode of the series of demonstrations of PILOTING's robotic solutions brings you BIKE, the crawler solution developed by WTR designed for internal inspection of pressure vessels.
Inspection of Large Structures	21/12/2022	AEROX	The last episode of the series of demonstrations of PILOTING's robotic solutions presents the AEROX experiment, an aerial platform developed by CATEC for its operation in the inspection of large structures.

Table 7. Public episodes of the PILOTING YouTube Series:” PILOTING Demonstrations & Experiments”

2.7 PILOTING I&M marketing campaign

During the period M19-M36, PILOTING has made an effort to increase the presentation of the project's main outcomes, using the websites’s News and Multimedia sections to this end.

In particular, a dissemination campaign was aimed at presenting the main result of the project: the PILOTING I&M platform, which is currently under development. The PILOTING I&M Platform marketing campaign pretends to disseminate the main content generated for the software platform designed to manage the mission of the robotic vehicles and control the operation. In this section, the latest multimedia content about this brand-new development can be found.

Up to this point, the most important dissemination actions that have been performed are:

- Presentation of the PILOTING I&M Platform workflow in the [5th newsletter](#).
- Presentation of the PILOTING I&M Platform at the Sprint Robotics World Conference (see Section 3.5).
- Presentation at PILOTING Innovation workshop (see Section 3.5).
- Presentation at the European Robotics Forum workshop (see Section 3.5).
- Presentation of the PILOTING I&M Platform at ROBOT 2022 (see Section 3.5).
- Elaboration of a video to the multimedia taps. [PILOTING I&M Platform – Workflow video](#): in this video, we can observe the workflow of the platform to digitize the inspection process; in particular, a real use case of visual inspection on a viaduct is shown.

The PILOTING I&M marketing campaign has been designed as part of the PILOTING business and industrialization plan, so you can read more detailed information about that in the deliverable D10.5 “Refined and Extended Business Plan” with a complete list of dissemination actions related with the PILOTING I&M platform marketing campaign.

3. Dissemination tools

3.1 PILOTING User Group

PILOTING Project User Group has greatly impacted the members by allowing them to improve networking and expand their capabilities. In addition, this has revealed some consequences like the increase of knowledge and other valuable contributions from a large set of external organizations and institutions.

The project has obtained benefits from the User Group due to the increase of the dissemination of their robotic platform developments or the spread of invitations for its events.

The information sent to the PILOTING User Group is managed by CATEC through the email address piloting-project@catec.aero. Even so, all PILOTING partners can share any information through the PILOTING User Group by contacting the Innovation, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (IDEM).

The PILOTING User Group list remains updated and accessible to all consortium partners in the project repository, Basecamp, in the file: Docs&Files → WP10 Exploitation, communication and dissemination → PILOTING User Group → PILOTING User Group list.

It is paramount to remark the increase of PILOTING User Group up of 215 members up to M36. Therefore, the target value defined in the proposal (150) has been achieved. The total increase of the members in the user group ascend to a 44% with 65 new members.

3.2 Publications

Within PILOTING, the project's main research outputs were disseminated through scientific publications in various journals and conferences.

During these two first periods of the project, 9 scientific publications were produced (4 in this second period), which is very close to the target value for the total project life cycle (10). Even more, taken into account that new publications will be generated from the first pilot experiments that were held in the second semester of 2022.

A list of the scientific publications during the M19-M36 period is presented in Table 8.

The scientific publications are provided in Green Open access. All publications are uploaded on Zenodo PILOTING Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/piloting/>).

TITLE	ABSTRACT	AUTHORS	INVOLVED INSTITUTIONS	REFERENCE	CATEGORY	PUB. DATE	STATUS
Localization System for Lightweight Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Inspection Tasks	This paper presents a localization system for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) especially designed to be used in infrastructure inspection, where the UAVs have to fly in challenging conditions, such as relatively high altitude (e.g., 15 m), eventually with poor or absent GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) signal reception, or the need for a BVLOS (Beyond Visual Line of Sight) operation in some periods. In addition, these infrastructure inspection applications impose the following requirements for the localization system: defect traceability, accuracy, reliability, and fault tolerance. Our system proposes a lightweight solution combining multiple stereo cameras with a robotic total station to comply with these requirements, providing full-state estimation (i.e., position, orientation, and linear and angular velocities) in a fixed and time-persistent reference frame. Moreover, the system can align and fuse all sensor measurements in real-time at high frequency. We have integrated this localization system in our aerial platform, and we have tested its performance for inspection in a real-world viaduct scenario, where the UAV has to operate with poor or absent GNSS signal at a high altitude.	Benjumea, D.; Alcántara, A.; Ramos, A.; Torres-Gonzalez, A.; Sánchez-Cuevas, P.; Capitan, J.; Heredia, G.; Ollero, A.	USE	https://doi.org/10.3390/s21175937	Conference Paper	3 Sept. 2021	Published
Aerodynamic Interference in Confined Environments with Tilted Propellers: Wall	Inspection and maintenance tasks are increasingly being carried out by multi-rotor platforms in order to avoid certain risks being taken by humans. In this way, it is necessary to have a good knowledge of the aerodynamic effects that occur when tasks are performed in confined environments. In addition, the use of tilted rotors is becoming more and more	A. Garofano-Soldado, G. Heredia, A. Ollero.	USE	Publication at AIRPHARO 2021 Workshop https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9571031	Conference Paper	4-5 Oct. 2021	Published

Effect and Corner Effect	widespread for tasks that require direct contact with a surface. In that sense, this paper presents several numerical simulations to analyse the aerodynamic performance of tilted rotors. In particular, the wall effect and the corner effect will be shown in detail. Two different configurations are considered in the corner effect: straight and curved corners. The influence of the corner and the wall has been studied for three tilt angles ($\theta=20^\circ, 30^\circ, 40^\circ$) and various distances between the rotor and the wall. Flow field visualization is depicted to understand the physical behaviour of the airflow.						
Aerial Robotic Solution for Detailed Inspection of Viaducts	The inspection of public infrastructure, such as viaducts and bridges, is crucial for their proper maintenance given the heavy use of many of them. Current inspection techniques are very costly and manual, requiring highly qualified personnel and involving many risks. This article presents a novel solution for the detailed inspection of viaducts using aerial robotic platforms. The system provides a highly automated visual inspection platform that does not rely on GPS and could even fly underneath the infrastructure. Unlike commercially available solutions, our system automatically references the inspection to a global coordinate system usable throughout the lifespan of the infrastructure. In addition, the system includes another aerial platform with a robotic arm to make contact inspections of detected defects, thus providing information that cannot be obtained only with images. Both aerial robotic platforms feature flexibility in the choice of camera or contact measurement sensors as the situation requires. The system was validated by performing inspection flights on real viaducts.	M. A. Trujillo, A. L. Petrus, D. Martinez, F. J. Garrido, A. Viguria and A. Ollero	CATEC	Publication at IRF2021 Conference https://zenodo.org/record/6390334#.YmKBOtpBxPY	Conference Paper	7-10 Nov, 2021	

<p>Numerical-experimental evaluation and modelling of aerodynamic ground effect for small-scale tilted propellers at low Reynolds numbers</p>	<p>In recent years, aerial manipulators with fully actuated capabilities are gaining popularity for being used in aerial manipulation operations such as critical infrastructure inspection or aerial manipulation tasks. Those scenarios usually demand the aerial platform to operate in constrained and narrow scenarios. It is well known that in these situations, the interaction of the wake generated by the propellers with the environment can significantly alter and change the performance of the rotors. Most studies have addressed this problem by considering the ground effect in hover conditions or during the landing maneuver for co-planar multirotor. However, few works analyze the behaviour of tilted rotors, which are used in fully actuated multirotor configurations thanks to their omnidirectional motion capabilities. This paper presents a numerical-experimental evaluation of the aerodynamic ground effect for small-scale tilted propellers at low Reynolds numbers. This aerodynamic effect has been experimentally evaluated through an extensive testing campaign in a testbench designed for this purpose which has been complemented by a CFD-based study. CFD results have been validated through a mesh independence study and a CFD-experimental propeller performance comparison. A numerical model has been also proposed to capture the dependence of thrust with distance to the ground and angle of inclination between the propeller and ground planes. We demonstrate that the proximity to the ground of tilted rotors decreases the thrust increment due to the ground effect as the tilt angle (θ) increases. This means that Cheeseman's classical theory is inapplicable, as it only considers the distance from the ground without reference to how the thrust increment changes with the tilt angle. This outcome enables future aerial robotic</p>	<p>A. Garofano-Soldado, Pedro J. Sánchez-Cuevas, G. Heredia, A. Ollero.</p>	<p>USE</p>	<p>https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1270963822002991</p>	<p>Conference Paper</p>	<p>11 May 2022</p>	<p>Published</p>
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	applications that strongly demand accurate aerodynamic effect models to operate close to obstacles and narrow environments.						
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Table 8. Papers published in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings

Apart from the publication previously mentioned, the PILOTING members have also developed open-source software libraries publications. The software publications are collected in the table below:

TITLE	Description of the publication	AUTHORS	REPOSITORY
Adaptation of the MAVSDK library to be used in the PILOTING H2020 project	This library is an adaptation of the MAVSDK library to be used in the PILOTING project. The PILOTING-MAVSDK C++ part consists of the core library implementing the basic MAVLink communication, the plugin libraries implementing the MAVLink communication specific to a feature and the examples implementing some examples of use of specific functions.	R. Caballero, F. Cuesta.	https://github.com/fadacatec/piloting-mavsdk
ROS wrapper of the MAVSDK library to be used in the PILOTING project.	This repository contains a ROS wrapper of the MAVSDK library to be used in the PILOTING project.	R. Caballero, F. Cuesta.	https://github.com/fadacatec/piloting-mavsdk-ros

Table 9. Open-source software publications in libraries

Moreover, PILOTING has also published open data sets and the interfaces of the PILOTING I&M platform in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/piloting/?page=1&size=20>) that fulfils the FAIR principles, as it was agreed in the Data Management Plan (deliverable D2.2). This publication of open data obtained from real experiments and the interfaces and data models of the PILOTING I&M platform is also a way to disseminate project results and increase its impact.

TITLE	Description of the publication	REPOSITORY
AERO-CAM Localization Dataset at Alora Viaduct	This dataset contains different flight sequences performed with the AERO-CAM platform on the Alora viaduct for the development of the PILOTING project.	https://zenodo.org/record/7432775#.Y6P22XbMJyw
Alora Bridge Dataset	Images taken by a drone from Alora viaduct	https://zenodo.org/record/7361562#.Y5C2nnbMJyw

A Scalable Data Management System Data Model facilitating the integration of any inspection system and the automated data digitalization process	The constructed document is attempted to present the designed Entity-Relationship-Diagram (ERD) of the DMS-DM. Additional definitions of the existing entities and the relations between them are also depicted.	https://zenodo.org/record/7351760#.Y5C28nbMJyw
A Versatile and Secure Data Management System API facilitating the Interconnection of any software component and Easy Data Access	The constructed document presents the communication endpoints (DMS API's Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs)) under which an authorized user can have access to the DMS API and subsequently to the collected data.	https://zenodo.org/record/7351723#.Y5C3T3bMJyw
VHR images were produced in the tunnel tubes of EOAE by autonomous robotic systems (2022)	This particular dataset is comprised of Very High Resolution (VHR) photos, gathered in the tunnel facilities of EGNATIA ODOS AE (EOAE).	https://zenodo.org/record/7350881#.Y5C3nHbMJyw

Table 10. Open data, interfaces and data models published in Zenodo

3.3 Organisation of workshops

PILOTING Project has continued the organisation of workshops within the dissemination activities framework in the M19-M36 period. A total of 3 workshops has been organized for the I&M community in different events.

Table 11 shows the 3 workshops organised within the PILOTING project in this period, this is one less than the workshops organized in the last period.

Workshop	Description	Date	Attendees
Challenges and opportunities in going from one-off deployments to Inspection and Maintenance (I&M) robotics in continuous operation at ERF 2022	Dr Antidio Viguria presented PILOTING I&M platform progress in the ERF2022 Workshop “Challenges and opportunities in going from one-off deployments to Inspection and Maintenance (I&M) robotics in continuous operation”.	28 th -30 th June 2022	>50 attendees

PILOTING Innovation Workshop	This workshop, organized within the project, presented the most promising value propositions from the technologies developed in PILOTING, obtain feedback from potential PILOTING end-users, confirm its assumptions, and select the most promising ones from among those identified.	11 th October 2022	44
I&M project session at ROBOT 2022	In the PILOTING framework, a workshop was organized at ROBOT 2022, where 5 I&M European projects presented its main results (RIMA, AERIAL-CORE, METRICS, PILOTING and ATLANTIS), in order to show to the general public the advantages of introduce robotics solutions in the I&M tasks.	24 th November 2022	32

Table 11. Workshops organized within PILOTING project 2nd period.

3.4 Large-scale demonstrations within PILOTING project

PILOTING proposes the adaptation, integration, and demonstration of robotic solutions, in an integrated platform for infrastructure inspection. One of the main milestones within the project is to complete large-scale demonstration of the technologies developed in the three scenarios: refineries, viaduct/bridges and tunnels.

Large-scale demonstrations have taken place to begin the validation of the robotic aerial platforms and the technologies developed within the project to give a solution to the identified use cases.

PILOTING Project recently concluded the first pilot experiments in the three scenarios. The PILOTING I&M platform was evaluated in the Álora viaduct in Málaga on July 26th as part of one of the large-scale demonstrations of the project. The first refinery demonstration occurred in September 2022 (from 12th to 16th) at the CHEVRON Oronite Plant (Gonfreville, France). Finally, the tunnel demonstration in Greece was validated from September 30th to October 7th.

These were the first real scenarios where these technologies have been validated, but a second set of experiments are expected to be performed by the end of the project. The multimedia material obtained during the experiments have been used to increment the dissemination of the project, both in project presentations but also in the website and social networks.

Additionally, during the course of the viaduct scenario demonstration, a workshop to present the project and the first results in the viaduct use cases were shown to stakeholders and external parties, including Directors from ADIF (the Spanish Public Railway Infrastructure company and one of the main customers of Ferrovial).

Figure 17. Experiments in the viaduct's scenarios, in the Álora viaduct in Malaga on 26th July

Figure 18. Experiments in the refinery's scenarios, in the CHEVRON Oronite Plant, in September 2022

Figure 19. Experiments in the tunnel's scenarios, in Metsovo, from September 30th to October 7th, 2022

3.5 PILOTING presentation at relevant events

Next, a brief description of the relevant events where PILOTING project has been presented. It is important to point out that PILOTING has been presented in 21 events (more than one per month) during this second period. This number increases in 60% the number of events in comparison with the first period (14 events).

EVENT	DETAILS	VENUE	DATE	Website
UNVEX 2021	<p>CATEC has participated in UNVEX 2021, the largest national event on UAS in Spain, presenting PILOTING in two different ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the whole event, FADA-CATEC set up a stand where some members gave all the interested attendants information about the project. • Furthermore, Antidio Viguria, the Project Coordinator, participated in a round table on “The future of the UAS sector through its applications”, where he presented its vision on the potential of UAS in Inspection & Maintenance applications and the main CATEC projects in this sense, among which PILOTING stand out. 	Spain	July 7 th - 9 th , 2021	https://www.unvex.es/
18th IRF World Meeting & Exhibition	Set in one of the world’s iconic cities, the 18th IRF World Meeting & Exhibition is a global summit & technology showcase that is focused on delivering solutions to the world’s pressing mobility challenges, while also supporting the long-term goals of energy efficiency, safety and sustainability in road design and operations.	Dubai, UAE	November 7 th - 10 th , 2021	https://worldmeeting.irf.global/

	At the IRF2021 CATEC presented the paper Aerial Robotic System for Complete Bridge Inspections, based in the last developments of the AeroX drone platform, one of the PILOTING vehicles.			
ASNT 2021: The Annual Conference	ASNT Conference is the largest NDT event, where industry professionals and hear industry experts present high-quality, innovative content. Waygate attended to this Conference and presented the project and the main developments it is carrying out.	Phoenix, Arizona, USA	November 15 th - 18 th , 2021	https://asnt.eventsair.com/asnt-2021-the-annual-conference/
RIMA and Sprint Robotics Seminar	Sigurd Albrektsen, SINTE presented PILOTING in a RIMA/Sprint robotics seminar with the theme Focus on Transport Infrastructure: Latest Developments in Robotics for I&M	Online	December 15 th , 2021	Focus on Transport Infrastructure: Latest Developments in Robotics for I&M Tickets, Wed 15 Dec 2021 at 14:00 Eventbrite
PIARC 2022 conference	INLECOM has presented its holistic, 3D tunnel deformation monitoring solution in a poster session. PILOTING has been disseminated, accordingly both in the event and also during the poster sessions.	Hybrid – Calgary, Canada, and Online	February 7 th - 11 th , 2022	https://program-calgary2022.piarc.org/en/program/at-a-glance
Amsterdam Drone Week 2022	Antidio Viguria, Project Coordinator, presented the main PILOTING outcomes in the “Energy&Utilities” session organized in the ADM2022. This session was focused on provide a wealth of knowledge on the latest project experiences and applications in the utility industry. Also, it showed interesting insights in the latest technologies and experiences in the field of BVLOS and the successful use of AI.	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	March 29 th -31 st , 2022	https://www.amsterdamdroneweek.com/
DRONExpo 2022	CATEC attended DRONExpo, a benchmark meeting for drone professionals and all their applications, designed to suit national companies in	Madrid, Spain	May 11 th -12 th , 2022	https://www.dronexpo.es/

	the sector, where they could present new developments, find opportunities for collaboration between companies and with administrations, promote projects and businesses, and be at the forefront of information on the future of unmanned technology.			
Visit from Chilean Delegation	On 13 th May, the Chilean delegation of the business cluster of the 40 largest companies in the country visited CATEC's facilities at its headquarters in Seville. During the visit, they visited the centre's facilities, from its laboratories to its offices. The representatives of the cluster showed their interest in the drone technology developed by CATEC in the field of robotic infrastructure inspection and maintenance.	Seville, SPAIN	May 13 th , 2022	N/A
ISUDEF 2022	ISUDEF, an international and multidisciplinary symposium, aims to address current issues on unmanned systems and the defence industry. PILOTING results were presented in a conference given by Antidio Viguria, Project Coordinator.	Madrid, Spain	May 30 th , 2022	https://aero.uc3m.es/https-2022-isudef-org/
RIMA and Sprint Robotics Seminar	Antidio Viguria, Project Coordinator, presented PILOTING in a webinar organized by Sprint Robotics within the H2020 project RIMA: "Cross-industry innovations for Storage Tanks". The title of its presentation was "Wall thickness inspection of tanks using aerial robots"	Online	June 21 st , 2022	https://www.eventbrite.nl/e/im-robotics-seminar-cross-industry-innovations-for-storage-tanks-tickets-344731951547
Expodrónica / World ATM Congress 2022	From 21st to 23rd June of 2022 it has taken place de World ATM Congress. The World ATM Congress is the world's largest international air traffic management (ATM) exhibition and conference. This	Madrid, Spain	June 21 st - 23 rd , 2022	https://expodronica.com/

	<p>event is a Civil Air Navigation Services Organisation (CANSO) partnership with the Air Traffic Control Association (ATCA). 110 countries from all over the world attended the congress celebrated in Madrid, Spain. CATEC has participated with a stand where some members gave all the interested attendants information about the project.</p>			
European Robotic Forum 2022	<p>The European Robotics Forum 2022 (ERF2022) is the most influential meeting of the robotics community in Europe. It was held from 28th to 30th June in Rotterdam, The Netherlands, and it covered all aspects and current themes related to the field of robotics.</p> <p>Dr Antidio Viguria presented PILOTING I&M platform progress in the ERF Workshop “Challenges and opportunities in going from one-off deployments to Inspection and Maintenance (I&M) robotics in continuous operation”.</p>	Rotterdam, The Netherlands	June 28 th -30 th , 2022	https://erf2022.eu/
Drones Webinars 2022 – Drones Technologies Webinar	<p>“Drones Technologies” is the first webinar of this series called “Drones Webinars 2022”, organised by MDPI.</p> <p>Dr Antidio Viguria was invited as a speaker to this session and presented GNSS free navigation advances in the framework of the PILOTING project.</p>	Online	June 30 th , 2022	https://drones-1.sciforum.net/
ETH Robotics Innovation Day	<p>The public RobotX event targets the Swiss industry and the research community at large where the latest developments of the ETH robotics labs are showcased. ETHZ team will be present and disseminate PILOTING through Roll-up.</p>	Zurich, Switzerland	July 1 st , 2022	https://center-for-robotics.ethz.ch/symposium.html

ETH Robotics Summer School	This summer school brings 25 ETHZ internal and 25 international master/PhD students. ETHZ partner will give a presentation to the students about the technical approach for the refinery ground monitoring robotic system.	Wangen an der Aare, Switzerland	July 04 th – 08 th , 2022	https://robotics- Summerschool.ethz.ch/
ONS (Offshore North Sea) 2022	During the ONS event, more than 65 000 visitors from around 100 countries gather in Stavanger. ONS assembles high-profile decision-makers as well as global influencers who are engaged in the world's energy discussion. SINTEF had a stand in the fair where PILOTING project and the navigation payload developed by SINTEF was demonstrated.	Stavanger, Norway	August 29 th - September 1 st , 2022	https://ons.no/
UNVEX 2022	In the 7 th edition of UNVEX fair, the organizers designed an event with a global vision on drones and RPAS due to the confluence of multiple technologies and many opportunities to create new demand.	Seville, SPAIN	September 14 th -16 th , 2022	https://www.unvex.es/evento-2022/
Sprint Robotics World Conference for Inspection and Maintenance Robotics	As part of the marketing campaign of the PILOTING I&M Platform, Antidio Viguria (PILOTING project coordinator) recently presented the PILOTING I&M platform in the Sprint Robotics World Conference for Inspection and Maintenance Robotics. This platform will be open-source next year.	Amsterdam, Netherland	September 27 th -28 th , 2022	https://conference.sprintrobotics.org/
Visit from EUROAVIA	EUROAVIA, a group formed by aeronautical engineers from the University of Seville visited CATEC's facilities and learned about PILOTING Project and the platforms and technologies that are being developed within the project.	Seville, SPAIN	October 24 th , 2022	N/A

RIMA and SINTEF Industry Day	SINTEF and RIMA arranged an open day for the Norwegian industry with focus on robotics in Inspection and Maintenance. SINTEF showed a virtual demonstration of the PILOTING tunnel inspection.	Trondheim, Norway	November 25 th , 2022	SINTEFs industridag for robotikk i inspeksjon og vedlikehold - SINTEF
ROBOT 2022	ROBOT 2022 was the Fifth Iberian Robotics Conference. Its main goal is to continue the precedent efforts in showing the robotic research and development of new applications in the Iberian Peninsula. Antidio Viguria, PILOTING Project Coordinator, presented the PILOTING I&M Platform, as part of the marketing campaign developed within the project.	Zaragoza, Spain	November 23 rd – 25 th , 2022	https://www.iberianroboticsconf.eu/

Table 12. PILOTING presentation at relevant events.

Figure 20. CATEC at ERF 2022.

Figure 21. ETH Robotics innovation Day PILOTING dissemination.

Figure 22. PILOTING presentation at ROBOT 2022

3.6 Awards and recognitions

➤ **Leonardo Torres Quevedo Award**

Aníbal Ollero Baturone, Director of the Robotics, Vision, and Control Group (GRVC) at the University of Seville, and partner of PILOTING project has been distinguished by the Ministry of Science and Innovation of Spain with the Leonardo Torres Quevedo National Award in the area of Engineering.

➤ **Sprint Robotics awarded WTR for groundbreaking collaborative work towards acceptance of inspection and maintenance robotics**

In this years' edition, the Sprint Robotics Committee has awarded a member of the consortium, Waygate Technologies, for its work in the field of “Groundbreaking collaborative work towards acceptance of inspection and maintenance robotics” alongside Petronas, in relation to the development in the field of PILOTING project, concerting BIKE robot.

Figure 23. Winners of the Sprint Robotics prize.

➤ **ENAIRE Foundation I+Dron Award**

This award recognizes works, studies, projects, articles or technical publications that constitute a unique contribution to innovation in the drone sector, in the fields of aircraft design and systems technologies (including propulsion, communications, control, etc.), production, operation, drone traffic management, as well as the development of new applications.

The award was given to FADA-CATEC for the work entitled “Cooperative Multi-UAV System for Surveillance and Search&Rescue Operations Over a Mobile 5G Node”, which incorporates some of the autonomous functionalities that are being developed as part of the PILOTING project. The team has been led by Miguel Ángel Trujillo and Antidio Viguria Jiménez, PILOTING Project Coordinator.

3.7 Clustering with other projects and initiatives

➤ [Robotics4EU \(H2020-ICT-2020-2, G.A. 101017283\)](#)

PILOTING Project Consortium has set a new collaboration with the European project [Robotics4EU](#).

The Robotics4EU Project aims to expand the use of AI-based robotic platforms in various fields such as healthcare, inspection and maintenance of infrastructure, agri-food, and agile production. To this end, they are analysing the acceptance of robotics solutions by society from a SoEL point of view.

The PILOTING consortium has maintained a collaboration with the Robotics4EU Project developers as part of the SoEL risks analysis since they can contribute from an experienced position about the application of robotic technology in society.

The collaboration between both projects will allow PILOTING to analyse whether there are any other requirements relating to SoEL that have not been addressed before and use the methodology and knowledge acquired by the Robotics4EU framework to analyse the SoEL risks inherent to the PILOTING Project. The work performed in this sense has been included in the deliverables D9.3 and D9.4.

In addition, it has been proposed the study one of the PILOTING uses cases using the maturity assessment that is being performed within ROBOTICS4EU, aligned with the development of the business plan. However, the ROBOTICS4EU Maturity assessment model is not complete in the moment this document is being submitted, so it is expected to appear in the next WP10 deliverable.

Figure 24. ROBOTICS4EU Project logo

➤ [RIMA \(H2020-DT-2018-1, G.A. 824990\)](#)

The inclusion of PILOTING dissemination content (videos, podcast, newsletter, etc.) in the [RIMA Community Network](#), an initiative boost in the RIMA H2020 project context, aims to connect and inspire key stakeholders in I&M robotics and accelerate innovation and uptake of robotics.

Figure 25. Example of PILOTING content in the RIMA Community Network platform.

PILOTING Partners	Contribution to RIMA Community Network
<p>FADA-CATEC</p>	<p>FADA-CATEC as the coordinator of the project has uploaded most of the content of the RIMA Community Network.</p> <p>In this content it is worth highlighting the information about the robots developed at CATEC.</p> <p>It is also important to mention the Podcasts and the Newsletters that figure in the platform.</p> <p>CATEC participated in an event named RIMA and Sprint Robotics Seminar on Cross-industry innovations for Storage Tanks. The webinar addressed the latest industry developments, challenges and successes.</p>
<p>USE</p>	<p>A profile has been created in the RIMA Community Network.</p>
<p>WTR</p>	<p>Publication of a YouTube videos about BIKE project. The inspection robot called BIKE is one of the key solutions Waygate Technologies brings into the PILOTING project initiative.</p>
<p>SINTEF</p>	<p>A profile has been created in the RIMA Community Network.</p>

Table 13. PILOTING content in the RIMA Community Network platform.

On the other hand, RIMA project has been presented in the ROBOT2022: the 5th Iberian Robotics Conference, focused on showing the robotic research and development of new applications. In this

event, FADA-CATEC, as project coordinator, has organized a session to present relevant I&M European projects, including RIMA.

➤ **[RESIST \(H2020-MG-2017-Two-Stages, G.A. 769066\)](#)**

Dissemination of the H2020 RESIST Project last Workshops through the PILOTING User Group. Below is the email that has been sent to PILOTING members to invite them to the event:

Dear PILOTING User Group Members,

PILOTING Consortium invites you to the dedicated workshop and the 2nd Pilot Demonstration by [RESIST H2020 project](#), on **Friday 20th May from 09:30 AM to 15:00 PM**. This event will be organised by ICCS and will take place in Turin, Italy.

The aim of this workshop is to present the main advances made in the framework of the RESIST project as well as to carry out a field demonstration.

The agenda of the meeting is the following:

- **09:30-11:50: Session 1: RESIST Workshop (at TECNOSITAF premises).**
 - 09:30-09:35: Workshop opening (FEHRL).
 - 09:35-09:45: Introduction to RESIST project (ICCS).
 - 09:45-11:40: Presentation of key components:
 - 09:45-09:55: RPAS and Ground Control Station (USE).
 - 09:55-10:15: Ultrasonic sensors and computer vision systems (CNR, TUG, GUF).
 - 10:15-10:25: REDComm Communication module (FORTH).
 - 10:25-10:35: RESIST Platform (ED).
 - 10:35-10:50: *Coffee Break*.
 - 10:50-11:00: Degradation models (ERRA)
 - 11:00-11:10: Structural model and condition analysis (DBA)
 - 11:10-11:20: Structural Vulnerability and Risk assesment (RISA)
 - 11:20-11:30: Cyber Security model (STS)
 - 11:30-11:40: Mobility Continuity mobile application (ICCS, BGU)
 - 11:40-11:50: Overview of pilot area, scenarios and demonstration (TECNOSITAF).
- **11:50-12:30: Lunch break.**
- **12:30-13:30: Transportation to St. Petronilla tunnel.**
- **13:30-15:00: Session 2: Pilot demonstration on the field.**

You can register to the event using the following link:
<https://www.eventbrite.fr/e/resist-workshop-2nd-pilot-demonstration-tickets-337259481187>

We are pleased to provide you with [COVID-19 Information for Visitors to Italy](#).

*Workshop connection details will be sent previously to the workshop date.

We are looking forward to welcoming you!

Best regards,

PILOTING Project Team

Dear PILOTING User Group Members,

I would like to invite you to the **RESIST Training Workshop** that will be held **virtually on 14 June 2022 at 10 am CET!** During the workshop you will have the chance to see the components developed within RESIST project in detail and consortium partners will provide a high-level training about their functionalities!

To register please visit: <https://www.eventbrite.fr/e/resist-training-workshop-tickets-352450979367>

Note: you will receive the ZOOM link to join the meeting, in the confirmation email.

Moreover, the **RESIST Final Event** is coming in a few days, on **24 June, 2022**. The Final Event's official invitation will follow, soon!

We'll be very happy promote the invitation to PILOTING User Group and join us!

Best regards,

PILOTING Project Team

Figure 26. Invitation emails to the H2020 RESIST Project last Workshops

➤ **IM-SAFE (H2020-NMBP-TO-IND-2020-singlestage, G.A. 958171)**

IM-SAFE is a H2020 project whose main objectives are to support the EC and the CEN to prepare new standards in monitoring, maintenance and safety of transport infrastructure. And secondly to coordinate and accelerate the process for enabling public authorities and supply-chain stakeholders in transport infrastructure to commit to the development and adoption of the new standards.

The consortium covers a network of all Europe's geo-clusters and represents all competencies needed to address the complexity and ambition of the Coordination and Support Action.

Figure 27. IM-SAFE H2020 European Project logo

- Ferrovia Construction, PILOTING partner, within the framework of the European **IM-SAFE** project, has organised a face-to-face event on November 17th, under the theme "Connected infrastructure: new forms of monitoring in Europe". Also, Antidio Viguria, as PILOTING Project Coordinator, also attended the event and participate in a round table. The event was attended by the most relevant players in the infrastructure sector.
- **IM-SAFE** project has been selected as the invited project for the 6th newsletter within the dissemination activities of the PILOTING Project, which will be published in February 2023.

➤ **BUGWRIGHT2 (H2020-ICT-2019-2, G.A. 871260)**

BUGWRIGHT2 H2020 Project has carried out a stakeholder meeting on the 6th of October 2021. This meeting main topic was named "The challenges of automation and artificial intelligence and more particularly of autonomous robots in the maritime sector for the inspection and maintenance of ships". PILOTING Project disseminated the event through the PILOTING social networks and PILOTING User Group and PILOTING partners participated in the event as attendants. See some examples in the Figure 28.

Figure 28. PILOTING social networks dissemination on BUGWRIGHT2 event 21/09/2022

➤ **Other collaborations:**

- Three different European projects related to robotics and I&M sector have been included as invited project in our newsletter: [DRONE4SAFETY](#), [AERO-TRAIN](#) and [ROBINS](#) (see Section 2.5).
- Also, a special session was organized at ROBOT 2022 (the 5th Iberian Robotics Conference) with 5 projects related to robotics and the I&M sector. These projects were: [RIMA](#), [AERIAL-CORE](#), [METRICS](#), [ATLANTIS](#) and [PILOTING](#). In these projects, it was possible to share the results and best practices of the different projects.
- Finally, [OMICRON](#) and [SAFEWAY](#) European projects were invited to participate in our PILOTING Inspection Gadget podcast (see Section 2.6.2).

3.8 Publication of potential results in the EC Horizon Results Platform

The European Commission has recently launched a functionality in the Participant Portal website that allows to publish the project results (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>) in order to promote PILOTING innovative solutions to third parties, including: visibility through Horizon Results Booster, Investor e-pitching events with Business Angel Networks, and connecting with the Enterprise Europe Network to multiply the matchmaking possibilities.

PILOTING partners have published the information (see Figure 29) related to the 10 final selected value propositions (see deliverable D10.5 for more details), which are:

1. V.P.1*: Quickly building 3D asset models.
2. V.P.2*: Mission Planning Interface.
3. V.P.3*: PILOTING I&M platform.
4. V.P.4*: Generic Robot Control Station or RCS.
5. V.P.5*: GNSS-free aerial robot navigation in large areas.
6. V.P.6*: Wall thickness measurements by aerial robots.
7. V.P.7*: Autonomous hand-wheel valve detection and manipulation.
8. V.P.8*: Installation of surveying targets by aerial robots.
9. V.P.9*: AI-based concrete defect detection, classification and segmentation.
10. V.P.10*: Navigation and mapping algorithms for GNSS-denied tunnels.

Figure 29. Project results published in EC Participant Portal

4. Monitoring of the KPIs

To complete the report addressed in the present deliverable, Table 14 summarizes the status of the KPIs after the second 18 months of the project.

<i>Communication/ Dissemination means</i>	<i>Targeted communities</i>	<i>Performance Indicators</i>	<i>Target Value</i>	<i>Reach level</i>	<i>Status</i>
Logo and Poster	General public	Logo and Poster designed	1 logo, 1 poster layout	International	Target achieved (see section 2.1)
Local media presence	General public	N° of appearances (TV, newspaper, radio, magazines)	One appearance per year per participating country	National	Achieved (see section 2.4)
Social media presence	General public	N° of posts performed, social media metrics (N° of followers)	One LinkedIn and one Twitter post per week, 500 followers	International	Post: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2021: Achieved 2022: Achieved Followers: 440 (LinkedIn) + 352 (Twitter) = 792

<p>Content delivery platforms (e.g. YouTube)</p>	<p>General public</p>	<p>N° of channels, performed posts</p>	<p>Project channel in at least one delivery platform with a minimum of 3 posts per year</p>	<p>International</p>	<p>2020: Achieved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video presentation of PILOTING project. • PILOTING partners' KOM interviews: 1st and 2nd part. <p>2021: Achieved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 PILOTING Youtube Series "Meet Our Inspection Robot" Episodes: Episode 1.- AeroX , Episode 2- CART Robot. Episode 3- BIKE, and Episode 4 – AEROCAM, • 1 PILOTING WORKSHOP S Video: European Robotics & AI workshop applied to Inspection and Maintenance. • 8 PILOTING Podcast "Inspection gadget" Episodes: Episode 1, Episode 2, Episode 3, Episode 4, Episode 5, Episode 6, Episode 7 and Episode 8. <p>2022: Achieved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 PILOTING YouTube Series "Meet Our Inspection Robot"
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					<p>Episodes: Episode 5 – RISING and Episode 6 – HYBRID.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 PILOTING YouTube Series “PILOTING Demonstrations & Experiments”: 1st large demonstration in the viaduct scenario Agenda, 1st large scale demonstration in the viaduct scenario, AEROCAM, UGV, RISING, HYBRID, BIKE, AEROX. • 1 PILOTING WORKSHOPS Video: PILOTING Innovation Workshop. • 1 PILOTING I&M PLATFORM Video: PILOTING I&M Platform - Workflow • 6 PILOTING Podcast “Inspection gadget” Episodes: Episode 9, Episode 10, Episode 11, Episode 12, Episode 13 and Episode 14.
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<i>Press releases</i>	Industry, general public	N° of press releases issued	One press release per year per participating country	National and International	2021: Achieved 2022: Achieved (see section 2.4)
<i>Newsletters</i>	Industry and Public Institutions	N° of newsletters released	2 newsletters per year	International	2021: Achieved 2022: Achieved (see section 2.5)
<i>Publications</i>	Research and Industry	N° of papers published	> 10 peer-reviewed scientific journals and conference publications	International	Almost achieved. 9 papers already published (see section 3.2)
<i>PILOTING User Group</i>	Industry	N° of participants	At least 100 members	International	Target achieved (already more than 215 members)
<i>Clustering with other projects</i>	Research and Industry	N° of projects collaborating with	RIMA DIH and at least three more projects	International	Achieved (clustering with 12 H2020 projects; see section 3.7)
<i>PILOTING workshops</i>	Industry and end-users	N° of workshops	At least three during the project	International	Achieved (4 in the first period + 3 in this second period; see section 3.3)
<i>Participation in relevant events</i>	End-users, standardisation bodies, public institutions, industry and research	N° of events per years	Participation in at least 2 events per year	International	Achieved (14 in the first period and 20 in the second period; see section 3.5)

Table 14. Dissemination and Communication KPIs

5. Conclusions

The deliverable D10.4 “Second Mid-term Dissemination Report” has provided an overview of the main dissemination activities addressed by the PILOTING Consortium, within the Dissemination plan defined in the D10.2 “Exploitation and Dissemination Plan”, during the second period of the project (M19-M36).

Having already overcome the COVID-19 pandemic the project came back to its normal course as it can be seen in the indicators reflected in this document where the PILOTING Consortium has done a great effort to comply with the objectives required. In the period M19-M36, dissemination activities, like publications of videos, podcast episodes, participation in events and publication of newsletters, have kept an outstanding performance being able to fulfil already most of the project dissemination KPIs (with still one more year left) improving in an important way the results obtained from the First Dissemination report, which contained the outcome from M1-M18 period.

In this regard, other assets have undergone important changes such as the website and the contents uploaded to social networks, which have improved the impact of the PILOTING Project on its target group. Related to the website, it has undergone several structural changes to accommodate the new audio-visual sections among other content.

An important effort was made in order to promote and give visibility to the project in social networks increasing the number of dissemination publications related to the videos uploaded to the website, participation in events and awards received by some of the partners. This effort has supported an important increase of the project impact, with a 30% increase of follower at LinkedIn, a 72% increase in Twitter and a regular impact of the website of 600 impressions (while in the first period this actually was the highest peak of impressions).

Finally, the clustering activities with other H2020 projects have also seen and set exceptional relations sharing experiences and knowledge and cross-dissemination activities with 12 European projects. Two high added value collaborations are worth highlighting: support of ROBOTICS4EU in SoEL impact assessment, and ROBOT2022 workshop with 4 other European projects where experience and best practices were shared.

Finally, PILOTING Project members will keep working on the dissemination tasks to optimize the dissemination of the project and increase project impact. As a continuation of deliverable D10.4, D10.6 will incorporate the dissemination actions and results during the last period from M37 to M48.

Annex I: PILOTING Public Presentation. New version.

PILOTING:
PILOTs for robotic INspection and
maintenance Grounded on advanced
intelligent platforms and prototype
applications

Grant agreement ID: 871542
Call for proposal: H2020-ICT-2018-20
Sub call: H2020-ICT-2019-2

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01 ABOUT THE PROJECT

WHY PILOTING?

EUROPE IS AGEING

European refineries and civil infrastructures, like tunnels and bridges, are gradually becoming deteriorated.

I&M

It is paramount important to increase the efficiency and quality of Inspection and Maintenance activities in order to keep the necessary safety levels.

MARKET SIZE

Inspection and Maintenance of Industrial Assets is 450 B € in Europe. It is necessary to increase productivity and quality at I&M in Oil&Gas and Civil/Transport Infrastructure sectors.

PURPOSE

PILOTING will develop complete solutions, based on intelligent plus highly autonomous robotic systems to perform Inspection and Maintenance operations in less time, reducing costs, improving the quality of inspections, and increasing the safety of operators. PILOTING will focus on end-users driven inspection and maintenance routine operations that are performed in large quantities and periodically.

**CHALLENGES
AND
OBJECTIVES**

02

PROJECT CHALLENGES

CHALLENGE 1

Reduction of current inspection costs and downtime

CHALLENGE 2

Production and access to reliable inspection data

CHALLENGE 3

Increase of personnel safety

CONSORTIUM

03

13 PARTNERS AROUND EUROPE

High reputation research and innovation partners together with worldwide leading technological companies, highly specialized SMEs, inspection and maintenance service providers and companies that operate or own infrastructures in both considered sectors (Oil&Gas and Civil/Transport Infrastructures).

04 USE CASES AND TOOLS

05 FUTURE EXPLOITATION

Main exploitable results:

- Robotic vehicles as inspection tools
- PILOTING I&M platform
- AI-based inspection algorithms
- Visualization portal

PILOTING I&M PLATFORM – VISUALIZATION PORTAL

THANKS

Follow the project updates:
<https://piloting-project.eu/>

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H2020 PILOTING
Project

